

A NEW APPROACH TO THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCES OF A MUSIC TEACHER

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Annotation: This article discusses new approaches to the formation and development of the professional competencies of a music teacher based on modern educational requirements. Today, a teacher is required not only to impart knowledge, but also to be a creative thinker, cultured, technologically literate and have communicative skills. Therefore, the article practically reveals modern directions of music pedagogy, innovative methods, the use of information and communication technologies, as well as reflective analysis and work on problem situations necessary for professional growth. It also emphasizes the importance of such competencies as continuous learning, self-assessment, creativity, emotional intelligence in the development of a teacher's personal and professional qualities.

Keywords: Music teacher, professional competence, innovative methodology, pedagogical technology, reflection, creativity, self-development, ICT, emotional intelligence, new approach, music, musical education, upbringing, spiritual and moral quality, musical culture, "competence", acmeological, creative, reflexive, technological, competent, psychological, andragogical.

INTRODUCTION

Increasing the professional competence of teachers at the modern stage of music education is one of the urgent issues. Because the quality of education directly depends on the teacher's knowledge, qualifications, pedagogical skills and desire to work on himself. Currently, traditional approaches are being replaced by new, creative and interactive methods. As a result of the reforms being carried out in our republic to develop the material and technical support of education, the creation of an information and educational environment, the development of information resources, the improvement of methodologies for their use in the educational process, the opportunities for students and teachers to use world educational resources are being expanded. In this regard, it is necessary for each specialist to have professional competence and to consistently improve it.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

So, what is competence? What qualities are reflected in the basis of professional competence? What qualities of competence should a teacher be able to demonstrate in himself. At the same time, this and related ideas will be discussed. "Competence" (English "competence" – "ability") is the effective use of theoretical knowledge in activity, the ability to demonstrate a high level of professional competence, skills and abilities. "Competence" as a pedagogical category entered the field of education as a result of psychological research. From a psychological point of view, competence means "how a specialist behaves in unconventional situations, unexpected (non-standard) situations, enters into communication, takes a new approach in relations with opponents, performs ambiguous tasks, uses information full of contradictions, has a plan of

action in consistently developing and complex processes.” Based on this, the following explanation is given to the category of professional competence. Professional competence implies the acquisition by a specialist of the knowledge, skills and qualifications necessary for the implementation of professional activities and their high-level application in practice. Professional competence implies the acquisition by a specialist of not only separate knowledge and qualifications, but also the mastery of integrative knowledge and actions in each independent area. The professional competence of a music teacher includes the following: In recent years, the number of scientific and practical works devoted to teacher competencies in the field of pedagogical education, in particular music education, has been increasing. The following sources serve as an important scientific basis for the development of the professional competence of a music teacher: The works written by N.A. Muslimov, R.J. Ishmuhamedov and M. Mirsolieva provide a deep scientific and theoretical basis for competence, innovative technologies, and professional growth in Uzbek pedagogy. Below is an analysis of the important ideas put forward in their books about competence: N.A. Muslimov et al. The main ideas and thoughts in “Pedagogical Competence and Creative Foundations”: pedagogical competence is defined as a core element of professional training. These competencies consist of a set of knowledge, skills, values and attitudes of a teacher and are necessary for the high-quality organization of the educational process. Pedagogical competence includes the following:

Methodological competence - the ability to select the content of the lesson and convey it using appropriate methods;

Psychological and pedagogical competence - taking into account age characteristics, arousing motivation;

Innovative competence - the ability to use new technologies and introduce innovations into the educational process;

Creative competence - the ability to freely express one's thoughts, find new solutions.

One of the important points made in the book: "Development of competence is not a one-time, but a process of continuous self-development and experience acquisition" R.J. Ishmuhamedov, M. Mirsolieva. The main ideas and thoughts presented in the book "Innovative educational technologies in the educational process": emphasize the need to organize innovative technologies on the basis of a competency-based approach. Educational technology is not just a method, but also the joint activity of the student and the teacher, in which competencies are formed. The book presents the following as the basis of the competency-based approach:

Not knowledge, but activity is important: the student should not receive knowledge, but be able to apply it in practice;

Teacher competence is the management of the teaching process, the use of communication, information technologies, and the stimulation of independent thinking of students;

Designing the educational process is the main competence of the teacher. Each lesson should be effective, goal-oriented and efficient necessary.

One of the important points made in the book is "Activating student activity using innovative technologies is the most important professional competence of a teacher." What does this give for a music teacher in these books? Muslimov and colleagues consider aspects such as a creative approach, innovative thinking and reflective analysis in musical and pedagogical activities to be

an integral part of competence. Therefore, a music teacher must constantly develop his professional competence in his work, through gaining experience. Music teachers should strengthen their professional competence by using innovative technologies such as interactive methods, ICT tools, and creative tasks to activate students in the lesson. The methodological recommendations presented in the book can serve as the basis for effective, interesting and purposeful organization of music lessons."

It is advisable to use the following methods:

1. Theoretical methods:

Analysis and synthesis – existing study existing theoretical sources and draw new conclusions based on their comparison.

Induction and deduction - developing scientific reasoning based on the general to the specific (or vice versa).

Classification - categorizing the teacher's competencies and determining their composition.

2. Empirical methods:

- Observation - analyzing the process of music lessons, seminars and practical exercises.
- Questionnaire and interview - conducting interviews with music teachers, collecting opinions and experiences.
- Experiment - applying new methodologies in practice and evaluating the results.

3. Innovative methods:

- Reflective pedagogy - updating the teacher through analyzing his own activities.
- STEAM approach - integrating art and technology into music education.
- Use of ICT - using digital technologies, online platforms, visual and audio resources in music lessons.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS.

In today's education system, the development of teachers' professional competencies is considered one of the urgent issues. In particular, a music teacher should be formed not only as a specialist who conveys musical knowledge, but also as a creator, motivator, psychologist and pedagogue. Research shows that the effective educational process directly depends on the set of professional competencies of the teacher. Important discussion points The need for new approaches is that traditional knowledge-based approaches are now being replaced by competency-based, activity-based and person-oriented approaches. In this case, the main goal is the development of students' independent thinking, emotional awareness and the opening of their creative potential.

The relationship between competence and creativity is that among the subjective competencies, creative competence requires special attention. Especially in music teacher lessons, the ability to create innovations, test new pedagogical ideas, and improvise is important. The role of innovative technologies, especially the organization of lessons through ICT (information and communication technologies), interactive methods, and electronic platforms, significantly

increases the competence of a music teacher. For self-development and reflection, the teacher's ability to constantly reflect on himself, that is, to look critically at his own activities and analyze them, is of great importance. This leads to the formation of metapedagogical competence. Analysis based on theoretical literature N.A. Muslimov and others noted that competence is not only knowledge, but also the art of using it correctly. This idea is especially relevant for a music teacher, meaning that each lesson should be a tool for arousing a creative approach, musical analysis, emotional impact, and aesthetic pleasure in art. Professional competence is a teacher's guarantee of high-quality teaching. A teacher with strong pedagogical and musical competence develops a high interest in subjects, solid knowledge, and a creative approach in students. Creativity is the heart of competence. An innovative teacher is a creative person who can carefully select new pedagogical approaches, musical games, technological tools, and has a personal methodology. ICT tools are a force that strengthens competence. The use of digital tools (musical software, audio analysis, video lessons, online singing and editing) turns a music teacher into a person who meets global, modern requirements. Communication with a student is a testing ground for competencies. Communicative competence is especially important in a music lesson - the student's musical worldview is formed through correct pronunciation, expression, rhythmic delivery, and establishing emotional contact. Competencies must be developed systematically. Professional growth must be continuous: the teacher updates his knowledge through courses, seminars, advanced training, and exchange of experience.

Modern approaches are implemented through:

Pedagogical competence - skills for effective and high-quality lessons for students;

Musical performance and theoretical knowledge - playing an instrument, melody analysis, musical literacy;

Communicative and emotional competence - establishing effective communication with students;

Information and communication competence - being able to use digital technologies in the classroom;

Reflective competence - analyzing one's own activities, identifying problems and trying to eliminate them.

Integrated education - teaching music in conjunction with other subjects;

Didactic games and practical exercises - ensuring the active participation of children;

Distance learning tools - teaching through interactive platforms;

Multi-level assignments - providing material individually depending on the interests and level of knowledge of students;

Professional development plans - planning and continuous growth of the teacher's activities.

Conclusion

The development of professional competencies of a music teacher is a process based on activity, reflection and continuous self-improvement. These competencies are strengthened through innovative technologies, a creative approach and personal methodology. It can be said that if a teacher develops his or her competencies, this directly has a positive impact on the musical thinking, aesthetic outlook and creative potential of students. In the development of professional

competencies of a music teacher, an analysis of the literature shows the need for in-depth study of the teacher's socio-cultural, technological and methodological skills. From a methodological point of view, the combination of theoretical-empirical and innovative approaches is of decisive importance in improving the quality of music education. The development of professional competencies is a continuous process that serves to increase the pedagogical, creative and technological potential of a music teacher. Innovative approaches, reflective analysis and new educational technologies ensure the quality and effectiveness of music education. Therefore, every music teacher needs to work on themselves, acquire new knowledge, and establish effective communication with students.

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